

DERLEME REVIEW
**EVALUATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA
PATIENTS USING BIOMARKERS AND
SCORING SYSTEMS**

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ABSTRACT

Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), typically arising from various pathogens causing respiratory infections, exhibits symptoms such as fever, cough, shortness of breath, and chest pain. The severity of CAP is often evaluated using scoring systems like Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI), CURB-65 Score, CRB-65 Score, and SMART-COP Score. Moreover, biomarkers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), lactate, and neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) are examined for their potential in reflecting the severity of infection and predicting mortality. CRP, as an inflammatory marker, increases in response to infections, while elevated lactate levels may indicate inadequate tissue perfusion. The NLR, representing the balance of neutrophils and lymphocytes, offers insights into the immune response. This paper underscores the importance of a multifaceted approach in evaluating CAP patients, considering both clinical scoring systems and biomarkers. While these indicators can provide valuable information, a comprehensive patient assessment should encompass various factors for personalized and effective treatment.

Keywords: *Community-acquired pneumonia, Biomarkers, Scoring systems, C-reactive protein, Lactate, Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio, Inflammatory markers, Mortality prediction*

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Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) typically defines the type of pneumonia acquired by patients in their homes or within the community. This condition arises as a result of an infection in the respiratory tract, often caused by various pathogens such as bacteria, viruses, or fungi (1-4). Community-acquired pneumonia is generally associated with the following symptoms, fever (an increase in body temperature), cough (particularly with or without sputum), shortness of breath (a sensation of difficulty breathing during respiration), chest pain (discomfort or pain in the chest region).

CAP is often treatable in healthy individuals. However, it can be more severe, especially in the elderly, those with weakened immune systems, or individuals with underlying health problems (1-4). Treatment typically involves antibiotics, antiviral drugs, or antifungal medications, depending on the specific type of pathogen causing the infection. Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment can often help prevent complications (5-7).

Scoring systems used for hospitalization of CAP patients are employed to assess the severity of the patient and determine appropriate treatment strategies (8-11). Here are some commonly used scoring systems for CAP patients:

Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI): PSI is a scoring system that assesses the severity of CAP. It includes various clinical and demographic factors such as the patient's age, comorbidities, vital signs, and laboratory findings.

CURB-65 Score: This scoring system uses the criteria of Confusion, Urea (>20 mg/dL), Respiratory Rate (≥ 30 breaths per minute), Blood Pressure ($<90/60$ mmHg), and age (≥ 65). Each criterion presence receives a score, and the total score determines the severity.

CRB-65 Score: Similar to CURB-65, this system includes altered Mental Status instead of Urea and assesses Confusion, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, and age.

SMART-COP Score: This scoring system is based on criteria such as Systolic Blood Pressure (<90 mmHg), Multilobar Infiltrates, Altered Mental Status, Respiratory Rate (≥ 30), Tachycardia, and CO₂ (Partial pressure of carbon dioxide <30 mmHg).

These scoring systems are commonly used in clinical practice to assess the patient's condition and determine severity. However, each patient should be individually evaluated, and the treatment plan should be customized based on their clinical condition (12,13). Similarly, laboratory parameters can be used in clinical decision making.

C-reactive protein (CRP) is a type of protein produced by the liver, and its levels increase in the body in response to inflammation or infection. CRP is considered an inflammatory marker, reflecting inflammatory processes occurring in the body (14-16). In the context of CAP, CRP levels can aid in assessing the severity of the disease and monitoring the response to treatment. CRP is regarded as an indicator of inflammation and is associated with conditions such as infections, inflammatory diseases, or tissue damage (1,17,18). The relationship between mortality and CRP levels is complex, as various factors can influence this relationship. However, in general, elevated CRP levels are often associated with more severe and advanced inflammatory conditions. This is important in evaluating the overall health status of the patient and their response to treatment.

Lactate is the ionized form of lactic acid, a salt of lactic acid produced in the body. Lactic acid is an acid formed during the process of anaerobic glycolysis, which is an energy production process from glucose without the use of oxygen. During this process, glucose is converted into lactic acid, resulting in the formation of lactate (19). Lactate levels in the bloodstream are generally low, but specific conditions or diseases, especially situations where tissue oxygenation is decreased, can lead to an increase in lactate levels. Elevated lactate levels can indicate inadequate tissue perfusion and metabolic disturbances (20,21).

In CAP patients, the relationship between lactate levels and mortality is often associated with the patient's clinical condition and overall health. Elevated lactate levels may suggest that the patient has developed severe complications, such as severe infection or septic shock. Various studies have shown that high lactate levels are associated with poor prognosis and high mortality, especially in severe infections and sepsis conditions (22). However, this relationship is not specific to CAP patients and is generally associated with infections (1,23). In CAP patients, an increase in lactate levels may suggest that the patient has developed severe complications. In this case, lactate levels can play a significant role in the clinical assessment of the patient and determining the treatment plan (24,25). However, specific and comprehensive studies are needed to establish a lactate level-mortality relationship specifically for CAP.

Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is a hematological parameter that expresses the ratio between the number of neutrophils and lymphocytes measured during a blood test. This ratio provides information about inflammatory conditions and the immune system's response. NLR is often used as an indicator of an inflammatory or immune response (26,27). Neutrophils and lymphocytes are essential components of the immune system, both being types of white blood cells (leukocytes). Neutrophils are typically associated with acute infections, while lymphocytes are generally associated with chronic infections and immune system responses (28,29). The relationship between the NLR and mortality in CAP patients has been examined in various studies (5,30,31). However, this relationship cannot be accepted as an exact and general rule due to the complexity of this interaction, and several factors can influence it.

Some studies have suggested that a high NLR may be associated with poor prognosis in CAP patients. However, due to the complexity of such relationships, it is not recommended to use NLR alone as a mortality prediction tool. It should be evaluated along with other clinical and laboratory parameters for a more accurate assessment (30,31). The patient's overall condition, comorbidities, age, gender, and other factors should also be taken into account.

As a conclusion the combined use of biomarkers and scoring systems can contribute to a more effective and personalized approach in the treatment of CAP. However, each patient is unique, and treatment plans should be tailored to individual characteristics and clinical conditions. Future research should focus on optimizing the use of these indicators and gaining a better understanding of their role in the management of CAP.

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